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THE SUCCESS OF RECORDING ARTISTICALLY GIFTED PUPILS AT THE GRADE LEVEL IN SLOVENE ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

In this paper, we discuss the recording of artistically gifted children in Slovene elementary schools. The recording of artistically gifted children took place by collecting drawings of children who were considered by the elementary education teachers to be artistically gifted. These artworks were evaluated for creativity and developed spatial abilities by an independent commission of experts in the field of art pedagogy. In the research, we were interested in the extent to which elementary education teachers' grades match the analytically obtained grades based on theoretically designed criteria for discovering artistic gifts. The research aimed to determine whether pupils (n = 103), who were recorded by teachers as artistically gifted, actually have developed abilities that determine artistic talent.

The research results show that the teachers covered by the research were not successful in identifying artistically gifted pupils. Recognizing artistic gifts caused them problems. Teachers are poorly acquainted with the concept of artistic talent and the characteristics of artistically gifted pupils. It has also been found that the subjective conception of beauty is at the forefront of teachers; however, they neglect the creativity aspect. The research findings showed that most teachers have misconceptions and insufficient knowledge about the elements that indicate that pupils are potentially artistically gifted.

Keywords: artistic gifts, recording of artistically gifted pupils, characteristics of artistically gifted pupils, creativity, artistic talent.

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INTRODUCTION

In the past, giftedness was conceived primarily as a natural asset that requires inherited good genes. (Yun Dai, 2003). However, today we know that giftedness cannot be just the genetic makeup of an individual but is influenced by many other factors; the transfer of gifted care to the school system was necessary. In recent years, Slovenia has also taken a slightly more committed approach to monitor giftedness at various education levels. In Slovenia, *Koncept odkrivanja in dela z nadarjenimi učenci* [The Concept of Discovering and Working with Gifted Pupils] (1999) is based on Marland's definition (1972), which states that gifted and talented children are those identified by qualified professional staff and have high abilities and high achievement abilities. We are aware of the fact that gifted pupils are in the minority. Still, for their preservation and development it is necessary to establish appropriate programs throughout the vertical of elementary education. As John Stuart Mill, the famous British philosopher, economist, and political philosopher, said, "it is necessary to provide good land on which they can grow." (Ravlić, 2018: 155). In the literature, we often find different interpretations of the terms giftedness and talent. Researchers believe that defining giftedness is a challenge in itself (Bailey et al. 2008), as in several selected studies there was not a single unambiguous agreed definition of what defines a gift and what talent. Definitions of giftedness varied according to the knowledge of its characteristics. One of the theoretical approaches of giftedness is Renzulli's theory of three rings, according to which this is a place of mutual overlap of ability, motivation, and creativity (Cvetković Lay, 2002). Renzulli (2016) says that above-average abilities, above-average creativity, motivation, and certain personality traits are necessary for exceptional achievements in specific areas of activity. In his three-circle model of giftedness, he distinguishes between general and specific. Koren (1988) understands giftedness as above-average competence in one or more abilities, while he considers talent as giftedness in one area. Therefore, talent is about specific giftedness. The artistic talents who will be the subject of our discussion are, therefore, pupils who show above-average abilities in the field of art.

Artistic giftedness

If we look at Renzulli's theory of three rings from the point of view of artistic giftedness, i.e., from the point of view of artistic talent, it is a

matter of mutual overlapping of motivation, creativity, and visual-spatial abilities. When it comes to motivation, we are talking about intrinsic motivation, which gives satisfaction and pleasure to the pupil while creating art, without external and internal pressures and without expecting special praise. We thus understand artistic creativity through artistic factors, which are a combination of personal qualities and artistic abilities. These are divided into factors that enable creativity (accurate perception, set of performances, imagination, and motor skills) and factors that promote creativity (sensitive perception, creative thinking, emotions, and motor sensitivity) (Duh, 2004). Developing creativity is one of the main tasks of fine arts lessons. As Grgurić and Jakubin (1996) say, artistic creativity and divergent thinking of all children, including the gifted, can be developed in regular lessons.

The general belief is that artistic giftedness is very easy to identify, but research, as well as practice, show the opposite. Although teachers and parents may quickly recognize a child's artistic gift, very little is done to help these children progress and develop their abilities. As with all other talents, it is necessary to include these children in programs where they can develop their abilities (Kuščević and Brajčić, 2018). It is important to maintain the idea that artistic talent is an ability that we must develop, and if we do not develop it, it is lost over time (Duh, Kljajič and Bratina, 2018).

In defining artistic talent, one can rely on several definitions of artistic talent. Maier described artistic talent with three key elements, namely artistic ability, motivation, and artistic creativity (Čudina-Obradović, 1991). As mentioned earlier, one of the key elements of artistic talent is the artistic ability, which is determined by spatial ability and the ability to think visually, collectively called visual-spatial ability. Artistic creativity is an element of artistic talent that enables the connection of ideas, information, and viewing things in an original, new, and unusual way. Thus, in visually gifted children, we notice that they are not satisfied with a single and easiest solution to a problem, but they seek all possible solutions in unusual ways (Maier, 1939; summarized by Duh 2004). Čudina Obradović (1991) states that the most important elements of artistic talent are motivation and creativity that gives something new, original, and personal to the artwork and is expressed as a dynamic, unintentional and independent creation of images in consciousness and the ability to communicate

aesthetically. Duh and Lep (2008) believe that artistic talent is a cross-section of above-average abilities, creativity, and motivation. In artistically gifted children, we notice certain characteristics that can guide us in recognizing. Thus, in pupils who are talented in the field of art, we observe an era of developed visual-spatial ability. These are expressed as a link between visual discrimination, visual memory, manual skills, and spatial abilities. Visual discrimination is manifested through an excellent observation of details, a very clear and precise first impression of a scene and an image, and it improves over the course of the experience. Visual memory is manifested through the ability to remember performances precisely as they are and the ability to revive and use them in thinking. Manual skills are observed through very good coordination of hands and eyes, and spatial abilities that allow the child to create in a three-dimensional space and see the relationships in it (Čudina Obradović, 1991). We also notice incredibly vivid imagination, memorization of extraordinary details, various images and things in their creation, not only flowers and houses. They spend a lot of time on artistic creation, and they like to try new art materials, means and techniques. They observe the world around them carefully and precisely and are very successful in doing so, setting very high standards for themselves (George, 1997). They are critical of their artworks; they express themselves consciously and in a controlled manner very early on. They always look for new, interesting, unusual art solutions, and they are not inclined to imitate. They often make several versions of artwork, and they use a lot of details. We can see rich narrative content, parallel projection, shading of objects and the use of different spatial keys (Berce Golob, 1994).

Discovering artistically gifted pupils

Discovering gifted pupils in the Slovenian school system also includes artistically gifted pupils. Some older research (Galbraith, 1992) shows that in Slovenia and Croatia, we were about 30 years behind in organizing the care system for the gifted (Vrgoč, 2002, summarized after Ravlić, 2018). From today's point of view, it seems that the care for the gifted pupils and artistically talented has come to life, at least in Slovenian elementary school curricula.

Discovering artistically gifted children involves recording, identifying, and obtaining the opinion of parents (Bežić, 2001). Usually, registration is carried out in the first and second educational period, and less often in the third (Bežić, 2003). In the first educational

period, based on the given criteria, teachers record pupils who they consider to be artistically gifted (Žagar, 1993). Visually gifted children can be identified during their artistic creation, as they show a certain level of artistic talent. Negru (2003) believes that this is best recognized in children around the age of 11. Experts from various fields are involved in the identification, and parents also play an important role (Bezić, 2001).

The first opinion is therefore given by the teachers who teach the pupil and based on that, they also register the pupils. Teachers have criteria that make it easier to register pupils, and they are also provided with specific characteristics of gifted pupils. In the recording phase, teachers do not test pupils with the help of tests and assessment aids (Žagar, 1993). After registration, the class teacher informs the parents about their child and obtains their opinion and consent for further proceedings (Bezić, 2003). Furthermore, artistically gifted children are identified through tests (intelligence tests, divergent production tests, achievement tests, learning tests, and criterion tests) and through the analysis of their artwork. For the reliable identification of artistically gifted children, it is necessary to take into account as many signs and factors as possible (Duh and Lep, 2008). As aforementioned, it is important that the artistically talented are identified as soon as possible and provided professional support. Those who recognize and teach artistically gifted must be experts in this field, receive lifelong education, and be aware of the importance of early identification of artistically gifted (Kuščević and Brajčić, 2018). After the identification, the school counselling service and the class teacher inform the parents and obtain their opinion.

Despite the fact that we know the process for discovering artistically gifted pupils and also know the characteristics of gifted pupils, many of them are overlooked. This raises the following questions: How to identify gifted pupils successfully, do all pupils show their potential, where do we meet these pupils, and in what environment will they show their potential? In doing so, we must emphasize the important role of teachers who spend a good part of the day with pupils and accompany them in various fields. Teachers who follow the child's development and efforts and achievements in individual areas get to know children well. Teachers are aware of the complexity of this task and, in many cases, do not feel competent for their quality performance. In the present research, we found that the recording of artistic talents by teachers in Slovenian pedagogical practice is certainly an issue.

DEFINITION OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

With an awareness that in the Slovenian elementary school space, similarly to Finland, too often special attention is paid to supporting pupils with learning difficulties (Tirri & Kuusisto, 2013), the identification of gifted pupils is somehow side-lined. Thus, research in the field of education is more focused on children with special needs and less on the gifted. In Slovenia, however, we have a detailed concept of discovering gifted pupils, which takes place in three parts, namely: recording pupils, identifying gifted pupils, and obtaining the opinion of parents. The same procedure applies to discovering specific talents in fine arts, i.e., to the discovery of artistic talents.

The process of discovering artistically gifted pupils largely depends on the teacher. Therefore we were also interested in which artworks teachers will evaluate as those that show artistic talent. So, with the help of the collected artworks, we wanted to assess the extent to which the grades of elementary education teachers match the analytically obtained grades on the basis of the theoretical design criteria for the discovery of artistic talent.

We collected 103 artworks from teachers. Some teachers provided several products for each pupil and some provided only one for some pupils. In our research, we wanted to assess and determine the extent to which the grades of elementary education teachers match the analytically obtained grades based on a theoretically designed criterion for the formation of artistic talent. We present only a part of a broader research, where we present the artworks of pupils identified by elementary education teachers in the regional unit Maribor of the National Education Institute of Slovenia as potentially talented, evaluated according to objective criteria.

METHODOLOGY

The research was based on how successful teachers are in recording artistically gifted pupils, what criteria teachers have for recognizing artistically gifted pupils, and whether classroom teachers recognize more artistically gifted girls or boys. The research is applied by purpose, as it is focused on solving practical cases and developing practice. According to the level of cognition, the research is causal-non-experimental. In the research, we used a qualitative and quantitative method of scientific-pedagogical research. We

surveyed 103 pupils on a non-randomized sample. Pupils attended the third and fourth grades of elementary schools at the regional unit Maribor of the National Education Institute of Slovenia in the school year 2017/2018.

We obtained artworks from 117 third and fourth-grade pupils, but after later data processing, we excluded 14 pupils due to the artwork's inadequacy, and therefore ended with 103 pupils. We collected a total of 187 artworks, as we obtained several artworks from some pupils.

The results obtained with the evaluation scale were classified into three groups:

- pupils in whom many characteristics of artistic talent are noticeable,
- pupils who have barely noticeable characteristics of artistic talent,
- pupils in whom the characteristic of artistic talent are not noticeable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When obtaining artworks for our research, we took into account that artistic talent is something we notice over a long period of time, and we need to know the child well. We asked elementary education teachers to select pupils from their class who they think are artistically gifted. We received several products from one pupil from some teachers, while we received only one product from others. The acquired artworks showed us on the basis of what criteria elementary education teachers evaluate and record potentially talented pupils.

In the following, we will present three artworks provided by teachers who were considered to show artistic excesses that can be attributed to artistic talent. From each group of pupils, one child's artwork is presented and analysed according to the noticeable characteristics of the pupils.

An example from a group of pupils in whom many characteristics of artistic talent are noticeable

Girl A was included in the group where many characteristics of artistically gifted children were noticeable. The girl made good use of the art technique in pencil drawing and used various technical procedures provided by the pencil during the creative process.

Figure 1: Girl A (10 years old). Pencil drawing.

In the drawing, she depicted a human figure in various positions, which she showed very well, as the details of the depiction of a human figure are quite diverse (body parts, clothes, roller skates). The girl showed movement with different body positions and movement speed, which is indicated by raised elbows and knees.

Figure 2: Girl A different ways of indicating the figure's movement

She also showed a movement that describes action - lifting a cat, and we also notice the coordination of movements of the body and its parts. Some drawing elements (roller skates) are very precise, which is an indicator of a good artistic memory.

Figure 3: Girl A Dynamics of figure representation

Well-developed spatial abilities are shown in the depiction of space. We can observe a partial overlap of drawn elements, open doors, and a rich rhythm.

Figure 4: Girl A Indication of spatial planes.

The girl also found a suitable artistic expression that has its suggestiveness and is well aesthetically organized. She filled the space completely. According to the observed artwork, we can

assume that the girl has well-developed motor skills, as some elements of the drawing are drawn very precisely. The drawing also shows soft and hard lines and artistic originality, but in the last depiction, we are surprised by flowers similar to stencils.

An example from a group of pupils in whom the characteristics of artistic talent are barely noticeable

The group of pupils, who have barely noticeable characteristics of artistic talent, included a drawing of a boy D. The boy made greater use of artistic technique and used various technical procedures provided by charcoal during the creative process. He used the possibility of shading, which can be seen on the right side of the face and part of the neck, and the possibility of quickly filling in the white areas, which can be seen on the clothes of the person being portrayed. The boy showed all the elements of the face, which express artistic originality and, in a way, expressiveness.

Figure 5: Boy D (10 years old). Charcoal drawing.

Some solutions to the art problem are original, unexpected, and individual. An uneven relationship between the head, shoulders, and neck can also be seen in the drawing. No parallel lines are observed when showing the mouth, but some unusual details are not typical of children at this age, namely the chin's display, which gives us a sense of space. The boy did not show the space by rhythm or overlap, but in a way, he established the space, as we mentioned

earlier, by showing the chin and shading. Different solutions of the same elements, such as eyes and ears, give us the feeling that we are looking at something special, something that has its artistic expression, and the expressiveness of the drawing's artistic expression.

Figure 6: Boy D Gradation of light values (left) and disproportionate size ratio (right)

It is also noticeable that the pupil does not yet have well-developed motor skills, as some lines are not very soft. What impressed us the most about this boy was the convincing expression, which aroused a special feeling in us, namely that the pupil solved the art problem in a completely original way. However, since we start from the assumption that artistic talent is an ability that has already been developed, we cannot yet talk about talent in this pupil. However, its development needs to be monitored.

An example from a group of pupils in whom the characteristics of artistic talent are not noticeable

The group of pupils in which the artistic talent's characteristics are not noticeable included the girl J's drawing. The girl made good use

of the art technique in the drawing and used various technical procedures provided by the felt-tip pen during the creative process.

Figure 7: Girl J (10 years old). Drawing with a black felt-tip pen.

As the central element, she showed a human figure in the drawing, which has all the necessary elements, but they are shown inaccurately. Orientation problems can be seen in the drawing of the figure's mouth. We can also notice problems with size proportions, as the head is slightly too large compared to the body's size.

We can also observe an attempt to display a movement that could indicate some action, in this case, running, but this was unsuccessful. The figure's clothes are defined, we can notice the texture, but we do not notice the details. The drawing's spatial distribution is demolished as the figure's size, architecture, road, and flowers do not make sense. Three-dimensionality cannot be seen in the drawing. The pupil has an averagely developed artistic expression for her age, which is not interesting. We also notice many stencil solutions, such as the sun, flowers, and clouds.

Figure 7: Girl J - Disproportionate head to body ratio

Analysis of the success of recording artistically gifted pupils

After a detailed analysis of all children's artworks obtained from 103 pupils, we obtained the following results:

In 7 pupils (6.8%), we observed many characteristics of artistic talent, of which 2 were boys (1.9%) and 5 girls (4.9%).

In 25 pupils (24.3%), we barely noticed any characteristic of the artistic talent, of which 6 were boys (5.8%) and 19 girls (4.9%).

In 71 pupils (68.9%), we did not notice the characteristics of artistic talent, of which 17 were boys (16.5%) and 54 girls (42.4%).

From the obtained results, we can conclude that the vast majority of teachers do not evaluate pupils' art products critically enough. They evaluate them too subjectively and not professionally enough. Most teachers do not recognize elements of artistic talent or do not recognize artistic originality and other qualities of children's artwork.

We should also compare the survey carried out 11 years ago (Duh, Lep 2008). The study included 85 children's artworks created by 63 third- and fourth-graders in elementary schools. A similar toolkit would be used to determine the success of recording artistic talents. We find that the results were fairly similar. Of all the children's artworks obtained, only a good tenth was those that have artistic

talent characteristics according to scientific criteria. It was found that elementary school teachers lack knowledge about the basic characteristics of the gifted, do not know the characteristics of quality artwork of children, and have a strong subjective view of art.

Table 1: Comparison of the performance of recording artistic talents over a period of 11 years

School year	No characteristics		Minimum characteristics		Characteristics of artistic talent		Total	
	f	f%	f	f%	f	f%	f	f%
2007/08	45	71.0	11	18.0	7	11.0	63	100
2018/19	71	68.9	25	24.3	7	6.8	103	100
Total	116	69.9	36	21.7	14	8.4	166	100

In summary, research conducted over a period of 11 years shows that teachers, in most cases, do not know and do not recognize important indicators of potentially artistically gifted pupils. The finding that the success of recording artistically gifted pupils in the present study was even worse than 11 years ago is, of course, worrying.

CONCLUSION

In the research, we found that teachers cannot identify potentially artistically gifted pupils, as only a small percentage of all collected artwork shows potential. Based on the artwork, the teachers could not judge which pupil shows that they are artistically gifted or shows potential. From this, we conclude that teachers do not know well enough the characteristics of artistically gifted pupils. When recording, they often rely on pupils' achievement in other subjects, although these do not necessarily mean artistic talent. Piirto (2007) finds that an individual's high IQ does not necessarily mean that they also have talent in a particular field. This also means that we should not limit ourselves to cognitive abilities reflected in the academic field in recognizing talent, but we should look more broadly across many other areas.

In the research, we also noticed that teachers do not have correct ideas about which characteristics of a pupil's artwork reflect artistic talent. Thus, we have observed that teachers put the subjective

conception of the beautiful at the forefront and neglect creativity in most cases. As a result, many stencil solutions can be seen in selected artworks. Teachers do not give an important role to the use of spatial keys, and they do not have adequate ideas of what quality children's artwork is, and, above all, they are not critical enough. We noticed that due to all the aforementioned reasons, the result was that teachers, in the vast majority, recorded girls as artistically gifted, in whom we observed many stencil solutions and drawing figures similar to cartoon characters. Based on the obtained results, we can conclude that teachers neglect boys' artistic potential due to subjective assessment, as boys' artworks are more expressive, which teachers did not recognize as artistic qualities, as solutions are unexpected for them.

In summary, research has shown that teachers, in most cases, do not know and have misconceptions about what are the important signs of a potentially artistically gifted pupil. Precisely because of this, it can happen that many real gifted pupils have already been overlooked. Ali Genç (2016) states that teachers should provide an appropriate environment for the development of creativity. An environment that would activate pupils' reflective thinking abilities, in which pupils could express themselves freely through both artistic and verbal means of expression. This would definitely help teachers in recording those who are more successful, i.e., potentially artistically gifted.

Given these findings, we are concerned about whether professionals in elementary schools are educated and follow the latest developments, whether they are sufficiently aware of the importance of early detection of artistically gifted children, and whether they know the characteristics of artistically gifted children. We also have fundamental questions: How many pupils with above-average art skills are registered in our elementary schools at all? It is worrying that a large number of pupils that were recorded as gifted are not.

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